

AEROBIC SOCCER SPECIFIC DRILLS ON PLAYING ABILITY AMONG ELITE AND SUBELITE SOCCER PLAYERS: AN EFFECTIVE STUDY

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Abstract:

The aim of the present study was to find out the effect of aerobic soccer specific drills on playing ability among elite and sub-elite soccer players. Thirty Soccer players were randomly selected from Nagercoil, Kaniya Kumari District. All the players are selected random and well experienced players who represented University level Competition (Elite) and District League (Sub-Elite). Their ranged from 21 to 28 years. All the Soccer players were divided in to the groups each group consist of ten players. Groups Namely Elite Group I (n=10), Sub-Elite Group II (n=10) and Control Group (n=10). Before and after the Soccer Specific Drills Programme for 6 weeks training the subjects were evaluated on Playing Ability (Experts Rating). Collected data were analyzed with suitable statistical tool for the final results. After the statistical treatment, it was concluded that the aerobic soccer specific drills highly influenced the Elite Soccer players on playing ability. Based on the results and conclusion it is recommended that the Aerobic Specific Soccer Drills proved to be very useful training for various levels of soccer player and it alert the overall playing ability.

Key Words: Soccer Specific Drills, Aerobic, Anaerobic & Playing Ability

Introduction:

Soccer is one of the world's most admirable sport, it consists of two teams trying to kick or head a round ball through opposing goals. (Scott Murray, 2010). The technique in soccer is a fundamental importance. Soccer technique covers all the methods of executing the movements that can occur when playing football. The primary characteristic of soccer technique observed directly Swami Vivekananda says that "You will be nearer to the heaven through a study of Geeta. The Soccer skills involved are simple, natural and yet one highly stimulating and satisfying to any child. These skills are kicking, dribbling, throwing, passing, trapping, heading and out writing an opponent (Thomas, 2006). The football game is played now-a-days in almost all countries having some differences in abided rules. The game which is played abided with the similar rules all over the world is known as soccer (Thomas, 2006)

Aerobics basically means living or working with oxygen. Some of these exercises include running, dancing, rowing, skating and walking. Aerobic exercise increases cardio respiratory fitness, which is the heart's ability to pump blood and deliver oxygen throughout the body. Some benefits of cardio respiratory fitness are increased endurance and energy. Weight control decreased blood pressure, decreased heart rate, decreased cholesterol levels, and an increased ability to manage stress. Evaluating Individual Playing Ability or performance within a team sport environment can present a difficult task for team sport coaches. The competence of player performance relies on the interplay of individual in tactical moves, the competence of players in the basic skills of catching, passing, kicking and tackling and in the more specific skills associated with particular playing positions. (Reilly, 1997). In Previous Studies, Coaches evaluation of playing ability has included an assessment of athletic ability only, or a combined measure of skills and physical capacities. Sawyer et al., (2002) related strength speed and power measures to coaches rating of football performance. In this Study, evaluation of football performance involved 2 specialized coaches providing a simple ranking of football players on their overall playing ability from highest to lowest rank. Players Ranking System is mainly used as a tool for assessing player skill levels and individual football playing ability. Ranking of playing ability by specialized coaches in the basis of match performance was used to differentiate levels of ability of football players. (Bakers et al., 1993; Sawyer et al., 2002)

Statement of the Problem:

The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of aerobic soccer specific drills on playing ability among elite and sub-elite soccer players.

Procedures: Subjects:

Thirty soccer players were selected randomly and participated in the study as subjects. All the players are selected random and well experienced players who represented University level Competition (Elite=10) and District League (Sub-Elite=10). Their ranged from 21 to 28 years.

Groups:

All the Soccer players were divided in to three groups each group consist of ten players. Groups Namely Elite Group I (n=10), Sub-Elite Group II (n=10) and 5 Elite Players and 5 Sub-Elite Players as Control Group (n=10).

Measurements:

Before and after the Soccer Specific Drill Programme for Six weeks, all the subjects were evaluated on Playing Ability (Experts Rating). In this Playing Ability, all the Soccer players were divided in to three teams consists of 10 each, in which 1 Goal Keeper, 4 Defenders, 3 Midfielders, 2 Forwards and played a Full 30 Minutes Match in front of Three Experts. The Experts will observe the playing ability based on the following aspects,

S.No	Criteria	Marks
1	Dribbling	10
2	Ball Control	10
3	Passing	10
4	Serving	10
5	Receiving	10
6	Defensive Technique	10
7	Knowledge of the Rules	10
8	Positioning	10
9	Assessing the Game	10
10	Over all Fitness	10
Total		100

Scoring:

The Scoring was made as per the average of the three experts rating taken at the time of the Full Match.

Training Procedure:

The Elite Group (n=10) and Sub-elite Group (n=10) were followed the training programme under the supervision of the investigator and the control group (n=10) were not exposed to any sort of these training programme.

Table 2

Aerobic Soccer Specific Drills	
S.No	Name of the Drill
1	Running with the Ball and Conditioning
2	Two Ball Drill
3	Six Ball Drill
4	Ladder Drill
5	Four-on-four Transition Drill
6	Conditioning with Dribbling
7	Pyramid Fartlek Run
8	Shuttle Run with Ball
9	Shuttle Run without Ball
10	Zig Zag Run

After the brief discussion with the experts in the field of football the Duration, Repetitions, Rest and the Week Duration were fixed. The Duration of the training period will be approximate 45 minutes per day in the Morning Session only. And weekly three alternative days for both the groups for Six Weeks. Both the Experimental training groups were trained the same set of training programme during the training period. All the above said Aerobic Soccer Specific Drills (Table: 2) were trained as per the schedule (Table: 3) given below.

Table 3

Duration	No. of Repetitions	Duration Per Repetition	Rest during Repetitions	Weeks
40 – 45 Minutes	3	60 Sec	2 Minutes	1 & 2
	4		3 Minutes	3 & 4
	5		3 – 4 Minutes	5 & 6

Statistical Analysis:

The mean and standard deviation (\pm SD) for the dependent variables of each study were calculated. Analysis of Co-variance was used to test significance difference between three groups, followed by Post Hoc Test.

Results: Analysis of Co-variance on Playing Ability:

Table 4

Test	Elite Group	Sub-Elite Group	Control Group	SV	SS	df	MS	F
Pre	60.80	62.00	57.60	between	103.47	2	51.73	1.56
				within	894.00	27	33.11	
Post	83.10	75.30	60.90	between	2536.80	2	1268.40	50.67*

				within	675.90	27	25.03	
Adjusted	82.80	74.47	62.03	between	2047.81	2	1023.90	53.46*
				within	498.00	26	19.15	
Mean Gain	22.30	13.30	3.30					

The Table values required Significance at 0.05 Level of Confidence for Degree of Freedom 1 and 27 and 1 and 26 are 3.22 and 3.23 respectively.

In Table: 4 the all the mean values of the Elite Group, Sub-Elite Group and Control Group on Playing Ability are tested Significance. Further from the table 4 proved that the calculated F Value of 53.46 for Playing Ability between the groups are greater than the Table Value 3.23 which indicates it is significant at 0.05 level.

Figure 1

Conclusions:

From the Analysis of the Study we can clearly observed that the Elite Group significantly superior than the Sub-Elite Group and Control Group in Playing Ability. This mainly happen because of the Load, Repetition and the Duration of the Training programme. Compare to Sub-Elite and Control Group, Sub-Elite Group had a better improvement in Playing Ability.

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